

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH DIFFERENT GAMES

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Abstract:

The present experimental study was researched to analyze the utilization of teaching through Language games on students' achievement in English. The research approach adopted is qualitative and quantitative analysis. The tool used to collect quantitative data is a questionnaire. The teachers' and students' opinion was collected through questionnaires related to research topic. There were interview held with English teacher which is tool for collecting qualitative data. According to findings, teaching English through the games method indicate many positive impact on improving their four language learning skills, vocabulary, critical thinking skills, team work skills and encouraging them to participate in the lessons.

Key words: play, stimulate, English, motivate, effective, creative, cooperative, advantage, at the same time, ability

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This article features multi-skill games that aim to teach English through stimulating, enjoyable, and purposeful play. The type, range, and complexity of the games mean they can be used to teach children from 3 to 12 years old. The paper is designed to allow teachers of English as a Foreign Language to move away from the traditional method of teaching, instead integrating games into the daily teaching schedule. A variety of games have been used, such as language games, competitive and non-competitive games, both traditional and newly invented, easy to more complex games, for when teachers are teaching a certain topic to different age groups. All of the games have been made with the aim of attracting the interest of children and moving them towards the desirable goal of learning English. Each game will have an aim, a language objective, and instructions for the teacher to follow. The games are tools for practice and language retention; they should be used to complement the many teaching methodologies.

It can be seen a lot of benefits of Teaching English through Games. In particular, the use of games as a teaching method has recently received considerable attention, not only in teaching children but also in teaching adults. "To a great extent, games can create a genuine desire to communicate in the targeted language, providing the learner with a strong motivation to do so. In this respect, games are usually competitive, with a clear winner or loser. This provides a challenge, and a challenge is motivating, as learners are more likely to put in greater effort if they are trying to accomplish a task which they find to be challenging". [2;49-51] If the challenge is too easy, they will soon grow bored and if it is too difficult, they may become frustrated. A good game will have the right level of difficulty for the players and they will be motivated to overcome this. This is ideal for language learning, since generally

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the more motivated a learner is, the more they will learn. Moreover, games can provide language practice in the various skills – speaking, writing, listening, and reading. Often these are restricted in the class, as for example in a traditional lesson a learner may be focusing too much on speaking and listening, with hardly any focus on reading and writing. “Games are an extremely useful supplement to more traditional teaching methods for this reason. They can also be used to enhance the value of repetition in learning, which can be ineffective and often demotivating, for the reason that during a game, the learner will be more willing to repeat something in order to improve and this will be rewarded with the chance to progress in the game”. [1;145]

There are various considerations for choosing games. Teachers should be aware of the reasons for using games when they are deciding whether a game will be effective with their students. There are a number of things to consider when selecting a game. First, they should look at why they are choosing the game. Clear objectives and language focus are essential. What is it that the teacher wants the students to practice and/or learn, and will this game provide that? Will the game be used to practice new language that has just been taught, and in this case implement it into the lesson plan? Alternatively, will it be used as a fun activity at the end of the day in which the students are still learning and practicing their English, yet being able to use the English that they have already acquired? This will have to be considered when looking at the type and difficulty of the game, and for what age group the game is suitable for. The teacher will also need to take into consideration how to best arrange students into groups. With simple games like bingo or tic-tac-toe it is effective for the whole class to play as a group. But for games with more complicated instructions and/or those that require discussion and opinion, it may be more effective to split the class into smaller groups.

To get better findings, questionnaires and interviews were done in several courses.” This study includes 120 participants, two English teachers from one of the high schools, in Samarkand. Data collection was done via the interviews and surveys with the intention of gathering information on the knowledge, attitudes and beliefs of students and English teachers regarding the use of games during ESL lessons. For this study, two different types of data collection strategies are employed: questionnaires with students and interviews with two English teachers. While we learned about the students' attitudes about games in ESL classes through surveys, we also sought to find out what the two English instructors thought about utilizing games to help their students with their English language abilities during interviews”. [3;5]

The eight questions on the questionnaire were designed to elicit the students' opinions and views about the usage of games in English classrooms. Students in the tenth and eleventh grades were given the questionnaires in various classrooms. After questionnaire, they felt excited and they would be participating enthusiastically.

“Open-ended interview questions enabled educators to share their thoughts freely and gather as much data as they could. The relevance and significance of games in English language schools were the topics of the inquiries”. [6]

The findings of the data analysis for each item are explored in depth in this section of the paper. As mentioned above, 120 students in the 10th and 11th grades from one of the high schools in Samarkand took part in the study. For this study, a questionnaire that consisted of eight questions was administered. The results of the student questionnaire will be shown in this section. As previously indicated, two EFL instructors from the same high school participated in a brief interview for this study about the use of games in English language instruction and their significance.

Undoubtedly, games have a place in the classroom. “They provide excellent chances for participation, exploration, and endeavoring; they also help students achieve high standards

in competitions and, most importantly, they help them develop their critical and creative thinking skills as they work to solve problems and their cooperative skills through role-playing". [5;20] Games as such do not have any downsides. They make the atmosphere happy and unforgettable. That being said, they can be challenging for instructors to oversee since, despite their best efforts to prepare ahead, games can still go longer than expected and cause issues. By looking at their facial expressions, teachers may tell whether children believe such games are pointless and juvenile. Even with a great deal of preparation going into the games, there may not be a common feeling in the class or there may be some really ambitious students, which might make others feel uncomfortable. To ensure that the students enjoy themselves while playing the games, it is advisable to briefly explain to them the benefits of each game, such as improving speaking abilities, among other things. "Numerous educators and linguists have devised various methods and strategies to facilitate the process of learning the English language. Using educational games in EFL lessons is one of the strategies they have discovered. There is consensus among the writers referenced in this study about the use of games in ESL instruction". [7] They discuss the advantages they provide as well as the proper methods for using them to fulfill their objectives. I believe that in order to keep learners engaged in English class, a variety of engaging tactics should be used and enable them to pick up the new abilities with ease. Playing games in an ESL class is one of these strategies. Nobody wants to spend their lessons without having a good time and enjoying themselves. Educational games are the ideal means of doing this. The teachers should choose games with the express purpose of imparting particular skills to the children. Games should have purposeful content to keep players' interest and help them develop critical skills. Here we will see some games that are beneficial for the lessons:

Scrabble

A word game that challenges players to create words using letter tiles and earn points based on the length and complexity of the words.

Taboo

A game where players have to describe a word to their teammates without using certain "taboo" words or phrases.

Word on the Street

A team-based word game where players have to come up with words that fit specific categories and move letter tiles towards their side of the street.

Unspeakable Words

A Lovecraftian-themed word game where players have to create words using letter cards while trying to avoid losing sanity points by using more difficult letters.

Last Word

A fast-paced word association game where players have to think of words related to a specific category before time runs out, testing their vocabulary and quick-thinking skills.

Word Slam

A party game where players have to guess a word based on the clues given by their teammates using a limited set of word cards, encouraging teamwork and creative thinking. [8]

The study's findings have shown that since gaming is a joyful and playful teaching method, English as a foreign language students gain a lot from using games in the classroom. These findings unambiguously show the value of game-based learning and its favorable impact on English language learners' attitudes. In conclusion, the study's findings demonstrate that, in addition to being a great way to help students relax in a classroom

setting, games can also be very beneficial to both students and teachers when they are designed with instruction in mind rather than just for fun.

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